

A Synthesis of *cis*- and *trans*-*dl*-1-*iso*Propylcyclopropane-1:2-dicarboxylic Acid and Experiments towards the Resolution of the *cis*-*dl*-Acid.*

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Direct evidence for the presence of *cyclopropane* ring in the various acids derived from thujane series of compounds has not been furnished so far. The object of the present investigation was to furnish such an evidence by synthesising the simplest member of this group of acids, *viz.* umbellularic acid.

Tutin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1104; 1908, 93, 252) found that umbellulone, on oxidation with permanganate, gave rise to a ketonic acid, umbellulonic acid, which yielded a lactone on distillation. Umbellularic acid was obtained from this lactone by oxidation with permanganate and had m.p. 120-121° (with 1 H₂O, 85°); [α]_D = -89.7° (in CHCl₃). Tutin excluded a *cyclopropane* ring structure for this acid on account of its marked stability to permanganate, hydrochloric and nitric acids and was inclined to regard it as 1-methyl-*cyclopentane*-2:4-dicarboxylic acid. Semmler (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 5019; 1908, 41, 3988), however, obtained by oxidising the benzylidene derivative of β -dihydrumbellulone, $\bar{a}$ -homothujadicarboxylic acid (I) which could only be the case if β -dihydrumbellulone and umbellulone were (II) and (III) respectively. From this it follows, that umbellulonic acid, the lactone and umbellularic acid are (IV), (V) and (VI) respectively.

(I)

(II)

(III)

* A short note on the synthesis of the *dl*-acid is in course of publication in *Nature*. We had started work on resolution of our synthesised acid when Rydon's note (*Chem. Ind.*, 1936, 55, 294) came to our notice and we have subsequently carried the resolution through. No details of Rydon's investigation have appeared till the date of writing this paper (21-5-1936).

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

A ready method of synthesising the acid (VI) would be to treat ethyl γ -bromo- α -isopropylglutarate or ethyl α -bromo- α -isopropylglutarate with concentrated alkali (Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 387). The results of Hariharan, Menon and Simonsen (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1928, 11A, 107) on the bromination of α -isopropylglutaric acid did not indicate this to be a promising line of attack. Adopting the method of Owen and Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1426; 1933, 1226) it was thought that ethyl α -isopropyl acrylate (VII) (Blaise and Luttringer, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1905, iii, 33, 648, 776) would condense with ethyl diazoacetate in the presence of copper-bronze to yield in one stage the diethyl ester of (VI). Though there was smooth reaction at 35° between the above substances the product consisted mainly of ethyl cyclobutane-1:2:3:4-tetracarboxylate (VIII) (*cf.* Owen and Simonsen, *loc. cit.*), about 70% of the acrylic ester remaining unchanged. This result is not very surprising in view of the fact that the success of Owen and Simonsen (*loc. cit.*) was largely due to the presence of *gem*-dimethyl group taking part in the desired cyclopropane ring formation.

Following the method of Auwers and collaborators (*Annalen*, 1929, 470, 284; 1932, 496, 27, 252), ethyl α -isopropylacrylate was condensed with ethyl diazoacetate to give ethyl 5-isopropyl- Δ^1 -pyrazoline-3:5-dicarboxylate (IX) in good yield. On heating at 200°, the latter lost nitrogen yielding the mixed esters, b. p. 144-148°/28 mm. Hydrolysis of this gave *trans*-*dl*-isopropylcyclopropane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid. The amount of *trans*-acid formed constituted about 35% of the hydrolysed product, the rest being a liquid mixture of unsaturated acids, the examination of which is as yet incomplete. The presence of α -isopropylglutaconic acid is to be expected in this mixture.

Condensation of Ethyl α -isopropylacrylate with Ethyl diazoacetate.—To a mixture of the substituted acrylic ester (12 g.) with copper bronze (0.5 g.), diazoacetic ester (9.6 g., b. p. 59°/25 mm. approx.) was added dropwise during the course of 3-4 hours, the temperature being maintained at 30-35°. The reaction was vigorous with evolution of nitrogen. After standing for some time, a fresh lot of the unsaturated ester (12 g.) was added and the diazo ester (9.6 g.) dropped as above. The experiment was repeated with another lot in the same flask with a fresh amount of catalyst (0.5 g.). After the addition was over, the temperature was cautiously raised to 50° and maintained at 50-60° for 3 hours. The catalyst was filtered off, and the product (50.4 g.) distilled, and the following fractions were collected: (i) 42-60°/5 mm., 21 g.; (ii) 95-105°/4 mm., 11.5 g.; (iii) 105-120°/4 mm., 2.5 g.; (iv) above 140°/4-10 mm., 1.5 g. with decomposition. Brownish black residue was left in the flask. Fractions (ii) and (iii) were mixed and redistilled: 3.4 g. distilled below 70°/2 mm. and the main fraction (9.10 g.) distilled at 85-100°/2 mm.

The main fraction was hydrolysed with methyl alcoholic potash (12%), when the potassium salt separated (2.5 g.). The acid isolated from the potassium salt melted at 274°, and was thus proved to be *cyclobutane-1:2:3:4-tetracarboxylic acid* (Owen and Simonsen, *loc. cit.*). From the alcoholic solution, after evaporation and acidification, 1.2 g. of a thick oil was obtained (b. p. 120-150°/26 mm.). The oil did not solidify on standing. It was unstable to neutral KMnO_4 .

Ethyl 5-isopropyl- Δ^1 -pyrazoline-3:5-dicarboxylate (IX).—The unsaturated ester (32.5 g.) was mixed with the diazo ester (24.5 g., 1 molecule each), in a three-necked flask fitted with reflux condenser and thermometer. There was no reaction in the cold. However, on warming the flask got heated up and when the temperature rose to 70°, it was cooled with water and the process of heating and cooling was repeated twice. Subsequently, the contents of the flask were maintained at 55° for 18 hours. The yellowish brown product was distilled, when the main fraction (33 g.) distilled constantly at 164°/4 mm. A small amount distilled at 45-60°/8 mm. and another fraction at 115-120°/6 mm. The main fraction was redistilled as a pale yellow viscous oil, b. p. 158°/1 mm.; n_D^{20} , 1.4814. (Found: N, 10.73. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.94 per cent).

The pyrazoline ester immediately decolourises cold alkaline permanganate and absorbs bromine in CHCl_3 . Attempt to isolate the

pyrazole derivative was not successful. The ester (5 g.) was dissolved in CHCl_3 (15 c. c.) and bromine (1.2 c. c. in 10 c. c. of CHCl_3) was added drop by drop, decolourisation occurred with evolution of HBr . After standing for 24 hours, the chloroform was removed under diminished pressure and the residue distilled in vacuum when decomposition occurred; main fraction $120\text{--}125^\circ/2$ mm. (ester was free from nitrogen).

Decomposition of the Pyrazoline Ester by Heat.—The ester was heated in 2 lots of 16 g. and 13 g. each at 200° for 1 hour when the product (15.2 g.) distilled at $148\text{--}155^\circ/30$ mm. (redistilled at $144\text{--}148^\circ/28$ mm.). The high boiling fraction ($170\text{--}200^\circ/30$ mm.) was again heated at 200° for 1 hour and on distillation gave 7.5 g. at $148\text{--}152^\circ/30$ mm, total yield 22.7 g. The ester, though unstable towards cold alkaline or neutral permanganate, does not take up bromine in CS_2 or CHCl_3 .

trans-dl-1-isoPropyl-cyclopropane-1:2-dicarboxylic Acid (VI).—The above ester (22.7 g.) was mixed with methyl alcohol (80 c. c.), water (17 c. c.) and KOH (17 g.) and refluxed on the water-bath for 1 hour. The alcohol was then evaporated off, the residue dissolved in water, acidified with sulphuric acid and repeatedly extracted with ether (6 times). After removing ether the residue partly solidified. It was distilled in steam for 15 minutes and the residue allowed to cool when the *trans*-acid crystallised out, yield 6 g. The yield of the *trans*-acid was not improved by using platinum as catalyst during pyrolysis of the ester (Kohler and Steele, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 1093). The mother liquors yielded a thick viscous oil, unstable to permanganate and distilling at $140\text{--}170^\circ/4$ mm. (8.5 g.).

The *trans*-acid when recrystallised from water separated in glistening rectangular prisms, m. p. $194\text{--}95^\circ$: A search for the *cis*-acid in the mother liquor did not meet with success (*cf.* Verkade, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1922, **41**, 208). It is easily soluble in alcohol, ether, acetone, difficultly soluble in CHCl_3 , benzene and water. Prolonged boiling with alkaline permanganate effected little change. [Found: C, 56.13; H, 7.20; Equiv., 86; M. W. (Rast), 185.1. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 55.82; H, 6.98 per cent. Equiv., 86; M.W., 172. Found: Ag, 54.95. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{Ag}_2$ requires Ag, 55.9 per cent].

cis-dl-1-isoPropylcyclopropane-1:2-dicarboxylic Acid.—The *trans*-acid (2 g.) was heated with acetyl chloride (5 c. c.) in a sealed tube for 3 hours at 180° . The anhydride of the *cis*-acid distilled at

140°/20 mm. (approx.) and at 113°/4 mm. It was a liquid which did not solidify (Tutin gives b. p. 167-69°/50 mm. for umbellularic anhydride). (Found : C, 62.03 ; H, 6.77. $C_8H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 62.33; H, 6.49 per cent).

The *cis*-anhydride dissolved in boiling water and the solution on cooling deposited the *cis*-acid. When crystallised from water the acid separated in prisms with 1 molecule of H_2O , which melted at 95° (sintering at about 85° ; complete fusion does not take place over a large range). (Found : C, 50.48 ; H, 7.81 ; H_2O , 9.97 ; Equiv, 94.3. $C_8H_{12}O_4$, H_2O requires C, 50.52 ; H, 7.41 ; H_2O , 9.47 per cent. Equiv., 95).

The anhydrous *cis*-acid obtained from an ethereal solution crystallises in plates from benzene-petroleum ether, m. p. 124-25° (shrinking at 121°). The acid is easily soluble in alcohol, ether, $CHCl_3$, CCl_4 , moderately soluble in benzene and water. (Found : C, 56.1 ; H, 6.90 ; Equiv., 85.86. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.82 ; H, 6.98 per cent. Equiv., 86).

The *cis*-acid on heating at 150° for 15 minutes loses water and goes over to its anhydride. It is stable to boiling alkaline permanganate. The *cis*-acid (0.1 g.) was heated with concentrated HCl (1 c. c.) at 180-190° for 3 hours (sealed tube). From the contents of the tube on opening, the *cis*-acid was isolated, m. p. 93°. Similarly it was isolated unchanged after heating with 8 times its weight of HNO_3 (3 parts of acid to 1 of H_2O) for 5 hours.

p-Toluil of cis-Acid.—The anhydride, obtained from 0.1 g. of the *cis*-acid by heating at 150°, was heated with *p*-toluidine (0.15 g.) for 5 minutes, the product treated with water and the *p*-toluil crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m. p. 89°. (Found : N, 6.35. $C_{15}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 5.76 per cent).

Resolution of the cis-dl-Acid with Brucine.—The *cis*-acid containing 1 molecule of water of crystallisation (3.25 g., 1 mol) was mixed with brucine (13.5 g., 2 mols; m.p. 178°) and dissolved in 230 c.c. of boiling water, filtered hot and allowed to cool; 6.1 g. of salt separated after a few hours. This was recrystallised from water 3 times. It gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -25.63^\circ$. It crystallised in plates from water, began losing water at 95° and melted at about 108°. [Found : N, 4.97 ; H_2O (at 130°), 14.5. $C_{54}H_{64}O_{12}N_4$, $9H_2O$ requires N, 4.99 ; H_2O , 14.1 per cent).

The free active acid was obtained by decomposing the above salt in the usual way. It crystallised in prisms from benzene. It gave $[\alpha]_D^{22} = +82.42$.

Since, however, the acid was not optically quite pure, it was again combined with brucine, the brucine salt was recrystallised and the acid liberated again, $[\alpha]_D^{21} = +87.7$.

The acid melted at 118° (prisms from benzene). It was obtained in thick needles by slow evaporation from water, m.p. about 83° (complete fusion not taking place). (Found: C, 55.91; H, 7.16. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.82, H, 6.38 per cent). From the mother liquors it was not found possible to isolate the *l*-acid with specific rotation greater than -66.6° .

Resolution of the cis-dl-acid with Cinchonidine.—The solution obtained from the *cis*-acid (1 mole, 2.4 g. containing $1H_2O$) and cinchonidine (1 mole, 3.7 g.) by boiling with 800 c.c. of water, was filtered, since no salt separated during 7 hours' standing it was concentrated to 300 c.c. when 4 g. of salt were deposited. This was recrystallised from water four times when 0.3 g. of salt was obtained as needles, m.p. 191° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.92. $C_{19}H_{22}N_2O \cdot C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires N, 6.00 per cent). The salt being very sparingly soluble in the usual solvents its rotation could not be taken.

The above salt was decomposed in the usual way and the active acid was obtained by extracting with ether. It showed $[\alpha]_D^{21} = -81.13^\circ$.

As the *l*-acid was not optically pure, the melting point of the acid (prisms from benzene) was rather low and was 114° .

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